

**Understanding Antibiotic Resistance:
Quantifying the Presence of the
sul1 Gene in *Escherichia coli*
and Analyzing its Effect
on the Bacterial Growth Rate
Under Different Concentrations of
Sulfamethoxazole**

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Abgabedatum: 31.01.2020

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Acknowledgements

I would like to offer my special thanks to Univ.Prof. Dipl.-Ing. Dr.-Ing. Jörg Krampe, head of the Institute for Water Quality and Resource Management at the Technical University of Vienna, for giving me the opportunity and allowing me to work in the laboratory. Additionally, I would also like to voice my gratitude to Ass. Prof. Mag. rer. nat. Dr. rer. nat. Norbert Kreuzinger, for overlooking the experiment process and arranging a time slot for my experiment. Last, but definitely not least, my very special thanks go to Msc Katarzyna Slipko, who supervised me throughout the experiment and aided me when handling the instruments. Without them, this work would not have been possible. I really appreciate their dedication and patience and the time they sacrificed from their work as well as work free hours to accommodate me.

Abstract

This paper focuses on understanding the mechanisms of antibiotic resistance in *Escherichia coli*, focusing on the presence of the antibiotic resistance gene *sul1* and its effect on the bacterial growth rate, as the increasing antibiotic resistance, mentioned in various media, is a cause for concern. The research question: “Are the number of *sul1* genes in the plasmids of *Escherichia coli* dependent on the exposure to antibiotic concentration of sulfamethoxazole and do the numbers of *sul1* genes/cell affect the growth rate?”, is answered through an empirical study, analysis and interpretation of obtained data, and literature research. The study shows that no general conclusion can be drawn from the results, as the individual strains behave differently. Although, an increase in *sul1* genes with increasing antibiotic concentration can be observed, it does not hold true for all strains. This can also be said for the effect of the number of *sul1* copies on the bacterial growth rate. These results show how challenging it is to counteract and understand the increasing antibiotic resistance as no clear pattern can be seen which could be applied to a numerous bacteria. Hence, it is of utmost importance to continue research in hopes of finding correlations that could give an insight on how to curb the spread of antibiotic resistance.

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Chapter 1

Introduction

1.1 Motivation

Since the discovery of the first antibiotic (AB), penicillin, in 1928 many more have followed and with them soon enough also resistance against these in bacteria. The wide application and misuse of antibiotics led to the spread of antibiotic resistance bacteria in human-related and environmental settings. Development of antibiotic resistance (AR) in pathogenic bacteria may lead to a failure of antibiotic treatment, considered a serious public health threat in the 21st century (World Health Organization, 2014). As I want to enroll in a study program in genetics and immunology and not least because of the frequent media coverage of the dangers of AR I found this topic highly interesting. During initial investigation of potential topics I discovered that the Technical University of Vienna was studying AR of bacteria in wastewater. After approaching them I was allowed to do an experiment at their laboratory under supervision by a researcher to ensure safety and to obtain guidance on the operations of lab equipment and machinery.

During the 1950s genetically transferable AR was first discovered in Japan (Davies & Davies, 2010): Dissemination of AR genes within bacterial populations occurs by vertical (during multiplication of a bacterial cell and inheriting the genetic material by a daughter cell) or horizontal gene transfer (through conjugation, transformation or transduction). Horizontal gene transfer enables bacteria to modify their genomes by acquisition of new genes, which may be connected to mobile genetic elements: plasmids, transposons or viruses (Norman, Hansen, & Sørensen, 2009). This allows bacteria to incorporate genes encoding resistance to certain antibiotics. According to the Antibiotic Resistance Database (ARDB), now incorporated into the Comprehensive Antibiotic Resistance Database (CARD), over 13.000 resistance genes of 377 types to 257 antibiotics were already discovered (Liu & Pop, 2009). Understanding mechanisms of AR genes dissemination is crucial in tackling the problem of AR emergence and spread.

1.2 Mode of action of antibiotics

There exist different mechanisms that allow ABs to inhibit further bacterial development. These can be through inhibition of cell wall synthesis, inhibition of protein synthesis, alteration of cell membranes and inhibition of nucleic acid synthesis (Kapoor, Saigal, & Elongavan, 2017). The first effective antimicrobials, sulfonamides, were introduced in 1937 (Davies & Davies, 2010). One prominent agent of them is sulfamethoxazole (SFX). It is a bacteriostatic antibiotic which inhibits the synthesis of dihydrofolic acid, by binding to dihydropteroate synthetase therefore, competing with para-aminobenzoic acid during dihydrofolate synthesis. The inhibited synthesized acid is a precursor of folic acid needed for both bacterial growth and the formation of DNA (Kemnic & Coleman, 2019). Hence, without the acid bacteria are unable to grow or replicate.

1.3 Mode of action of the *sul1* gene

A gene that studies have shown to cause resistance against SFX is the *sul1* gene. It was found present in Gram-negative bacteria including *Escherichia coli* (*E.coli*) (Hammerum et al., 2006). It uses antibiotic target replacement as a resistance mechanism and is commonly associated with class 1 integrons. Integrons are able to change and add new genes into bacterial chromosomes (Cambray, Guerout, & Mazel, 2010). Forty percent of the sulphonamide resistant *E.coli* samples isolated from humans were found to have the *sul1* gene (Hammerum et al., 2006).

1.4 Problem statement

The emergence and dissemination of AR in bacteria are considered as a serious public health issue that may lead to a failure of antibiotic treatment making surgeries, transplantations, even simple interventions, injuries and infections life-threatening. The nodes linking human-related bacteria with environment are wastewater treatment plants (WWTP), which are reported to be among the main sources of antibiotic resistance released into the environment (Karkman, Do, Walsh, & Virta, 2018). The presence of antibiotics and other substances adverse to bacteria (e.g. heavy metals, disinfecting agents), together with the close contact of pathogens and environmental bacteria proliferating in the biological stages in WWTP, may provide a selective environment for antibiotic resistant bacteria (ARB), antibiotic resistance genes (ARGs), and gene transfer (Karkman et al., 2018). Discharged WWTP effluents have repeatedly shown to contain ARB and ARGs (Barancheshme & Munir, 2018; Bengtsson-Palme et al., 2016; Rizzo et al., 2013).

Escherichia coli in wastewater was found to be resistant to a wide variety of antibiotics (Reinthalder et al., 2003). It was hypothesized that through ingestion it can find its way into animals and then

from their meat into humans (Hammerum et al., 2006). Therefore, it is important to observe and understand the systematics behind the acquisition of AR. One should focus on finding attributes in bacteria that cause an advantage in AR compared to wild type bacteria, as well as on understanding these, to enable tackling AR mechanisms. A thorough understanding of these mechanisms would also help improving future antibiotic synthesis and guidelines for the prescriptions for drug intake.

Studies suggest that resistance of *E.coli* against a different AB, ciprofloxacin, is linked to the presence of the *qnrS* gene and with an increase in antibiotic concentration, there is an increase in *qnrS* expression in plasmids within bacteria. Thus, enabling them to survive higher antibiotic selection pressures. Plasmid free strains, on the other hand, showed no resistance (Kaplan, Marano, Jurkevitch, & Cytryn, 2018). Thus, there seems to be a relation between the abundance of plasmids, carrying the *qnr* gene, and survival of bacteria in the presence of antibiotic selection pressure. A similar correlation might hold true for the *sul1* gene, as it is also present in the plasmid of bacteria and encodes for resistance to the antibiotic SFX. Understanding the correlations between the number of copies of the gene, AB concentration, and bacterial survival, would be of high importance to understand AB resistance.

Additionally, as the exposure to AB puts bacteria under selective pressure the energy required to survive would be focused on expressing a higher number of *sul1* copies, this reduces the energy available to continue to grow and divide.

Hence, the following **research question** is posed: **Are the number of *sul1* genes in the plasmids of *Escherichia coli* dependent on the exposure to antibiotic concentration of sulfamethoxazole and do the numbers of *sul1* genes per cell affect the growth rate?**

Hypothesis: *E.coli* exposed to a higher antibiotic concentration have a higher number of plasmid-mediated *sul1* gene copies, which reduce the rate of growth.

Chapter 2

Methodology

2.1 Study design

The study is performed in the laboratory of the Research Unit of Water Quality Management at the Institute of Water Quality and Resource Management at the Technical University of Vienna under supervision of a qualified professional who ensured that the experiment is conducted according to the safety standards. As the area of investigation is new and barely, if any, papers are available, the supervisor at the university aided in the design of the experiment, specifically with the correct dilutions, concentrations and settings for the machines. It is conducted in three phases depicted in Figure 2.1: (1) *E.coli* is isolated from wastewater processed in the lab by plating on media with chosen sulfamethoxazole concentrations. (2) The resistant bacteria are picked and checked for presence of the *sul1* gene through colony-PCR. (3) *E.coli* strains that contain the *sul1* gene (as well as chosen negative ones acting as the control group) are grown in broth with varying antibiotic selection pressure, undergo plasmid extraction and are checked for the number of copies of *sul1* genes through qPCR. This allows us to determine the correlation between the number of present *sul1* genes and the observed antibiotic resistance. The individual phases are described in more detail below. For the precise protocol of the experiment please refer to Appendix B.

2.2 Phase 1: Growth of bacteria under different AB concentrations

In this phase (comprising of steps 1-11 of the detailed experiment protocol provided in Appendix B) wastewater is diluted, by adding different amounts of saline (step 9 in the experiment protocol), and then filtered with a filtration system (Figure 2.2) through a membrane, to ensure a reasonable

Figure 2.1: Study design

concentration of bacteria per plate. This process ensures that there are enough bacteria colonies that are isolated and spread out to be picked without cross contamination. The system is connected to a pump which absorbs the redundant effluent. The membrane is then placed on a medium suitable for growing *E.coli*, chromogenic coliform agar (CCA), which was mixed with different concentrations of SFX (0, 1, 10 & 100 mg/L). The concentrations constitute the independent variable. The plates are incubated to later pick isolated colonies from. After phase 1 *E.coli* colonies will appear blue to violet on the membranes, making them distinguishable from other coliform bacteria, which appear from pink to red. Figure 2.4a and 2.4b show colonies after growth under different concentrations of SFX. Figure 2.4a shows the bacterial growth of *E.coli* at concentrations 10 and 100 mg/L SFX (at a saline dilution of 10⁰). Although the top row plates grew under the same conditions, the bacteria in the plates differ in number and density, due to natural variation. Colonies that are isolated are preferable to pick in order to avoid cross-contamination. Therefore,

the upper right plate is not as suitable as the left one. Figure 2.4b shows bacterial growth under 0 and 1 mg/L SFX (at a saline dilution of 10^{-1}). In all 4 plates the number of *E.coli* colonies is moderate and spread out making them suitable for single colony picking.

Figure 2.2: Set up of filtration system for dilution of wastewater in phase 1

2.3 Phase 2: PCR and *sul1* testing

In phase 2 (steps 12-19 in experiment protocol, Appendix B) isolated *E.coli* colonies are picked from each concentration to be subjected to PCR, in order have multiple copies. After PCR, the selected colonies undergo electrophoresis and are checked for the presence of *sul1* under a transilluminator depicted in Figure 2.3. After phase 2 the strains attested for the *sul1* gene are identified. Based on the results of colony-PCR (Table 2.1 and Figure 2.3), control strains, which do not contain *sul1* gene, and test strains, which tested positive for *sul1* gene, are chosen. The strains with a positive signal for *sul1* appear bright (17, 21-24), as well as the strain labeled M (Marker) (aiding as a comparison) and PC (Positive Control), showing that no contamination took place.

Strains were labeled with numbers: 1, 2, 3 (control group, no SFX exposure on the agar medium) and 17, 21, 22, 23, 24 (test group, with strain 17 being subjected to 10 SFX, 21-24 to 100 SFX).

Figure 2.3: Ultraviolet transilluminator photograph of the electrophoresis to check for presence of *sul1* gene in strains 1-24 (strain numbers have been overlain on the original photograph for better interpretability)

2.4 Phase 3: Plasmid extraction

In phase 3 (steps 20-30 in the experiment protocol, Appendix B) the 5 colonies which tested positive for *sul1*, as well as 3 control strains (strains 1-3, considered ‘wild types’ not having been put under AB selection pressure) are grown in Luria-Bertani (LB) broth and again subjected to all 4 SFX concentrations. Two samples were taken from each broth, which results in 64 samples (8 strains times 4 SFX concentrations, each sampled twice). To ensure the same cell number in each broth at the beginning of incubation, optical density (OD) is measured. Results are close to 1 for each strain (Table 2.2). Each strain is incubated with each chosen concentration of SFX. The samples undergo plasmid extraction with a specialized kit to ensure the copies of *sul1* are in the plasmid and not in the chromosome. The resulting extracts undergo qPCR to check the number of *sul1* copies per ml of broth. At the end of phase 3 the number of *sul1* copies per ml of broth is known, constituting the dependent variable. This allows us to analyze the relationship btw. the number of *sul1* copies obtained and the SFX concentration the bacteria were subjected to.

(a) Bacteria growth at concentrations of 10 (top row) and 100 (bottom row) mg/L SFX

(b) Bacteria growth at concentrations of 0 (top row) and 1 (bottom row) mg/L SFX

Figure 2.4: Plates at the end of Phase 1 (Step 11) with *E. coli* grown at different SFX concentrations

Table 2.1: Results of test for *sul1* gene presence after PCR through electrophoresis in strains (step 19)

Strain	SFX in medium	test for <i>sul1</i>
1	no SFX	negative
2	no SFX	negative
3	no SFX	negative
4	no SFX	negative
5	no SFX	negative
6	no SFX	negative
7	1 SFX	negative
8	1 SFX	negative
9	1 SFX	negative
10	1 SFX	negative
11	1 SFX	negative
12	1 SFX	negative
13	10 SFX	negative
14	10 SFX	negative
15	10 SFX	negative
21	10 SFX	negative
17	10 SFX	positive
18	10 SFX	negative
19	100 SFX	negative
20	100 SFX	negative
21	100 SFX	positive
22	100 SFX	positive
23	100 SFX	positive
24	100 SFX	positive

Table 2.2: OD value of strains per stock to ensure an equal amount of bacteria

Strain	OD of Stock
1	$9.80E-01$
2	$9.79E-01$
3	$9.16E-01$
17	$9.05E-01$
21	$1.02E00$
22	$1.02E00$
23	$9.97E-01$
24	$9.24E-01$

Chapter 3

Evaluation of *sul1* presence, ABR and growth rate

3.1 Determining the number of *sul1* copies

Following theoretical preparations and the study design, the experiment was performed in the first half of July 2019 in the laboratory of the Research Unit of Water Quality Management at TU Wien. The materials used in the experiment are listed in Appendix C. Results of qPCR are summarized in Table 3.1 (after logarithmic transformation, so the differences between the groups are easier detectable) and depicted in Figure 3.1. The number of *sul1* copies/ml of broth is calculated based on qPCR results by taking the copies/ μ L of DNA extract and multiplying it by 100 (the volume, in μ L, of elution buffer used to elute the plasmid (cf. experiment step 31 in Appendix B)). The result is then divided by 2, as two ml of broth are used from the plasmid extraction as a sample. Then, the log of the average number of copies/ml of broth is calculated for each strain. No standard deviation, in form of error bars, is shown in Figure 3.1 as only 2 samples per strain were tested, which are not enough to calculate a proper standard deviation. Refer to Appendix D for all results from qPCR.

In Figure 3.1, the increase of *sul1* copies/ml of the broth can be observed for all tested strains, as the concentration of SFX increases. However, within tested strains, 2 groups can be differentiated based on the intensity of their response to the selection pressure (strains 17, 21 and 24 vs. 22 and 23). Note, that strain 17 was initially subjected to a concentration of 10 SFX during growth on the agar plates, whereas strains 21-24 were grown on agar containing a concentration of 100 SFX. Thus, the trend of higher presence of *sul1* genes in AR colonies of *E.coli* is clearly visible. Of those colonies grown under SFX 10 concentration only one strain (17) tested

Figure 3.1: Log. number of *sul1* copies per strain at different concentrations of SFX in mg/L ($\pm 0.1\text{mg}$, $\pm 1\mu\text{L}$)

Table 3.1: Logarithmic number of *sul1* copies per ml (± 0.1 ml) in each strain

Strain	0 SFX	1 SFX	10 SFX	100 SFX
1	2.36	4.22	4.07	4.87
2	4.12	3.53	4.06	4.87
3	3.85	3.39	3.79	4.65
17	8.57	8.40	8.47	9.21
21	8.47	8.46	8.77	8.97
22	7.36	7.03	7.10	7.48
23	7.40	7.24	7.32	7.58
24	8.27	8.31	8.31	8.71

positive, whereas all but two strains grown under SFX 100 tested positive. However, the quantitative analysis via qPCR produces a less clear picture, with strain 17 showing similar numbers of *sul1* gene presence, as strains 21 and 24. The other two strains (22, 23) show a lower presence of the *sul1* gene. Given the number of samples analyzed, a test of statistical significance is required to see whether the observed differences are significant. Some further reflections on potential reasons for the unexpected differences in *sul1* presence in strain 17, compared to those exposed to higher levels of SFX concentrations is provided in Section 4.1.

3.2 Testing for statistical significance

In order to evaluate the statistical significance of the results, ANOVA test was used (a two-way test run with the p-value set at 0.05). The strains were grouped into 3 groups: Group 1 (G1) are strains 1-3 which are the control group; Group 2 (G2) are strains 17, 23 and 24 which tested

positive for *sul1* and also showed a strong increase in the number of *sul1* copies; Group 3 (G3) are strains 21 and 22 which were tested positive for *sul1* but, did not show an equally strong increase in the number of *sul1* copies as G2. The groups were compared to each other, and compared within the group, using antibiotic concentration and the group as factors.

As shown in Table 3.2, and as expected, there is no significant difference between the behavior of strains of G1 at tested SFX concentrations. The strains of G2 showed a significant difference in number of *sul1* copies at a concentration of 100 mg/L SFX (Table 3.3). When comparing strains of G3 (Table 3.4) they are significantly different at almost all concentrations, apart from concentrations of 10 and 1 mg/L SFX. This may point to a basic resistance already in G1 via different resistance mechanisms, as further discussed in Chapter 4. In Table 3.5, G1 is compared to G2 and surprisingly the only significant difference occurs at 100 mg/L SFX. There is a significant difference between G1 and strains G3 at all concentrations, as seen in Table 3.6. Table 3.7 shows that there is a general significant difference between G2 and G3 at all antibiotic concentrations.

Table 3.2: ANOVA two-way significance test within control group G1
(strains 1-3) per SFX concentration

SFX	t	P	P<0.050
SFX 100 vs. SFX 0	3.21E-04	1.00E00	No
SFX 100 vs. SFX 1	3.20E-04	1.00E00	No
SFX 100 vs. SFX 10	3.07E-04	1.00E00	No
SFX 10 vs. SFX 0	1.33E-05	1.00E00	No
SFX 10 vs. SFX 1	1.32E-05	1.00E00	No
SFX 1 vs. SFX 0	7.54E-08	1.00E00	No

Table 3.3: ANOVA two-way significance test within control group G2
(strains 17, 23 and 24) per SFX concentration

Comparison	t	P	P<0.050
SFX 100 vs. SFX 0	4.192	0.003	Yes
SFX 100 vs. SFX 1	4.394	0.003	Yes
SFX 100 vs. SFX 10	3.751	0.007	Yes
SFX 10 vs. SFX 0	0.441	0.888	No
SFX 10 vs. SFX 1	0.643	0.896	No
SFX 0 vs. SFX 1	0.202	0.842	No

Table 3.4: ANOVA two-way significance test within control group G3
(strains 21 and 22) per SFX concentration

Comparison	t	P	P<0.050
SFX 100 vs. SFX 0	3.776	0.011	Yes
SFX 100 vs. SFX 1	7.377	<0.001	Yes
SFX 100 vs. SFX 10	6.378	<0.001	Yes
SFX 10 vs. SFX 1	1.000	0.337	No
SFX 0 vs. SFX 1	3.601	0.011	Yes
SFX 0 vs. SFX 10	2.602	0.046	Yes

Table 3.5: ANOVA two-way significance test btw. G1 and G2 by SFX
concentration

SFX	Group	t	P	P<0.050
SFX 0	2 vs 1	1.604	0.128	No
SFX 1	2 vs 1	1.402	0.180	No
SFX 10	2 vs 1	2.045	0.058	No
SFX 100	2 vs 1	5.796	<0.001	Yes

Table 3.6: ANOVA two-way significance test btw. G1 and G3 by SFX
concentration

SFX	Group	t	P	P<0.050
SFX 0	3 vs 1	9.667	< 0.001	Yes
SFX 1	3 vs 1	5.722	< 0.001	Yes
SFX 10	3 vs 1	6.816	< 0.001	Yes
SFX 100	3 vs 1	13.781	<0.001	Yes

Table 3.7: ANOVA two-way significance test btw. G2 and G3

Group	t	P	P<0.050
G2 vs. G3	4.006	0.002	Yes

3.3 Determining the growth rate

To analyze whether the number of *sul1* genes in the plasmids influence the growth rate (μ) the OD is measured for each sample in regular time intervals after incubation: 0 minutes (T_0), 90 minutes (T_1), 150 minutes (T_2), 210 minutes (T_3), 270 minutes (T_4) and 330 minutes (T_5). At time T_4 the stationary phase is already reached but the measurements are needed for DNA analysis, namely to calculate *sul1* copies per cell. This is mentioned later in this chapter.

Table 3.8: The measured OD of all samples in the chosen time intervals

Strain	SFX	T_0 OD	T_1 OD	T_2 OD	T_3 OD	T_4 OD	T_5 OD
1	0	0.042	0.089	0.275	0.829	1.007	1.300
1	10	0.051	0.105	0.465	1.000	1.142	1.192
1	100	0.045	0.092	0.458	0.867	0.930	0.869
2	0	0.037	0.071	0.160	0.602	0.962	1.153
2	10	0.031	0.082	0.279	0.851	1.090	1.008
2	100	0.039	0.066	0.320	0.769	0.842	0.752
3	0	0.046	0.170	0.445	0.738	0.981	0.981
3	10	0.048	0.139	0.492	0.849	1.032	1.062
3	100	0.051	0.165	0.495	0.789	0.831	0.758
17	0	0.038	0.074	0.162	0.644	1.071	1.054
17	10	0.038	0.075	0.194	0.762	1.144	1.183
17	100	0.061	0.065	0.232	0.758	0.968	0.862
21	0	0.036	0.065	0.160	0.760	1.225	1.220
21	10	0.033	0.068	0.185	0.761	1.159	1.145
21	100	0.032	0.050	0.188	0.713	0.996	0.888
22	0	0.037	0.080	0.198	0.818	1.118	1.203
22	10	0.040	0.018	0.343	0.961	1.149	1.076
22	100	0.057	0.080	0.301	0.874	0.945	0.905
23	0	0.036	0.084	0.335	0.904	1.093	1.105
23	10	0.037	0.093	0.475	1.009	1.057	0.999
23	100	0.050	0.092	0.430	0.873	0.884	0.830
24	0	0.047	0.069	0.178	0.814	1.093	1.158
24	10	0.065	0.068	0.212	0.878	1.104	1.044
24	100	0.052	0.059	0.325	0.859	0.938	0.886

Table 3.8 shows the measured OD of all samples at the chosen time intervals. A general increase of OD is noticeable as time goes on, which is to be expected, as the bacteria continue to grow. This is also visible in Fig. 3.2 as an upwards slope is visible for all strains at all SFX concentrations. However, at T_5 the OD reduces again as the death, or decline, phase is reached where the bacteria number starts to decrease.

With the measurements from Tab. 3.8 the growth rate is calculated by subtracting the natural log of the measured OD at time b by the measured OD at time a , which is then divided by the difference in time (see Equ. 3.1).

$$\mu = \frac{\ln(ODb) - \ln(ODa)}{\Delta t} \quad (3.1)$$

Table 3.9 shows the growth rate of the exponential phase for the samples using Equ. 3.1. For strains 1 and 3 an increase in μ is observable, as the AB concentration increases. In comparison, a decrease is observable for strains 17, 21 and 22. The remaining strains, 2, 23 and 24, behave differently as there is neither a continuous decrease or increase in growth rate, as the AB concentration increases, but instead there are fluctuations. For strain 2 there is a decrease at 10 mg/L of SFX, when comparing μ at 0 mg/L SFX. However, the μ at 100 mg/L SFX is higher than at the other AB concentrations. Strain 24 behaves similarly and strain 23 has a greater μ at 10 mg/L SFX than at 0, but decreases at 100 mg/L SFX. The reason for the discrepancies of the growth rate is further explored in the next chapter 4.

Table 3.9: The growth rate of the strains under different AB concentrations during the exponential phase

Strain	0 SFX	10 SFX	100 SFX
1	0.019	0.025	0.027
2	0.022	0.019	0.026
3	0.015	0.024	0.026
17	0.023	0.023	0.021
21	0.026	0.024	0.022
22	0.024	0.022	0.022
23	0.023	0.027	0.026
24	0.025	0.024	0.029

Then, the doubling time (t_d) is calculated using the following equation:

$$t_d = \frac{\ln(2)}{\mu} \quad (3.2)$$

,where the natural log of 2 is divided by the growth rate (Widdel, 2010). In order to get the exponential growth phase the time interval with the lowest t_d is taken. After having found the lowest t_d it is cross-checked with the corresponding graph in Fig 3.2. It has to correspond with the linear part of the curve to be the exponential phase. Table 3.10 summarize the chosen time intervals for the exponential phase and Tab. 3.11 states the according doubling times for each strain. Strains 17, 21 and 22 have an increasing t_d with and increasing AB concentration. For strain 1 the opposite holds true as t_d decreases with increasing AB concentration. The remaining strains 2, 3, 23 and 24 again, behave differently with each AB concentration. Strains 2, 3 and 24 experience an increase in t_d at 10 mg/L SFX and then a decrease at 100 mg/L SFX. The remaining strain 23 has a different pattern to all other strains as t_d decreases at 10 mg/L of SFX, but then increases at 100 mg/L SFX, although t_d is lower than at 0 mg/L SFX.

Table 3.10: The chosen intervals for the exponential phase of each strain,
under each AB concentration, according to the t_d

Strain	SFX	Time interval
1	0	T1 to T2
1	10	T1 to T2
1	100	T1 to T2
2	0	T2 to T3
2	10	T0 to T1
2	100	T1 to T2
3	0	T0 to T1
3	10	T0 to T1
3	100	T0 to T1
17	0	T2 to T3
17	10	T2 to T3
17	100	T1 to T2
21	0	T2 to T3
21	10	T2 to T3
21	100	T1 to T2
22	0	T2 to T3
22	10	T1 to T2
22	100	T1 to T2
23	0	T1 to T2
23	10	T1 to T2
23	100	T1 to T2
24	0	T2 to T3
24	10	T2 to T3
24	100	T1 to T2

Table 3.11: The doubling time (t_d) for the exponential phases of strains
under different AB concentrations

Strain	0 SFX	10 SFX	100 SFX
1	36.774	27.973	25.922
2	31.368	32.507	26.240
3	24.009	29.330	26.451
17	30.074	30.458	32.813
21	26.684	29.378	31.164
22	29.357	30.820	31.382
23	30.029	25.519	26.904
24	27.322	29.300	24.271

After having calculated the desired t_d , the number of cells needs to be calculated for all measured times. This is done using the following formula:

$$N = N_0 \cdot 2^{\frac{t}{t_d}} \quad (3.3)$$

Where the number of cells at time t is calculated by multiplying the number of cells at time 0 by 2 which is raised to the power of the time t divided by the corresponding t_d . Knowing the number of cells at T_4 , the *sul1* copies/ml from a second run of qPCR is divided by cells/ml resulting in the number of *sul1* copies/cell. Note that strains 2 and 3 were excluded as time and equipment was limited in order to run multiple runs of qPCR. The detailed results for the second run of qPCR can be found in the Appendix D.

Table 3.12: The average number of *sul1* copies/cells in the samples at different SFX concentrations

Strain	0 SFX	10 SFX	100 SFX
1	0.000	0.000	0.000
17	0.619	0.518	0.762
21	1.455	0.980	0.827
22	0.029	0.075	0.073
23	0.028	0.021	0.066
24	0.667	0.806	0.636

Using the data from Tab. D.3 the amount of *sul1* copies per cell can be calculated. The results are summarized in Tab. 3.12. Overall it can be said that strains 17, 21 and 24 have the highest average number of *sul1* copies/cell, which is also visible in the previous graph Fig. 3.1, although the graph depicts copies/ml and the copies/cell stem from the second run of qPCR. When comparing the amount of copies/cells to the growth rates of the individual strains (Tab. 3.9), some discrepancies arise.

Strain 1 shows no copies at all which would match with the original PCR results (Tab. 2.1) where strains 1-3 tested negative for *sul1* presence. However, when looking at the growth rates for strain 1, the bacteria still managed to grow under all tested SFX concentrations. Strain 17 has a higher number of *sul1* copies when no SFX is present, than when it is exposed to 10 SFX and has the same μ at both AB concentrations. At a concentration of 100 SFX the amount of copies increases, but the growth rate decreases. Strain 21 shows a different behavior, as with increasing AB concentration the amount of *sul1* present and the growth rate reduces.

Strain 22 experiences an increase in copy-number as AB concentration increases from 0 to 10 mg/L SFX however, at 100 mg/L SFX the copy-number is lower than at 10 SFX, although minimally. This is also mirrored in the growth rate as it does not change from 10 to 100 SFX, yet is higher at 0 SFX, where a lower number of *sul1* copies are present.

The number of copies for strain 23 decreases minimally at 10 SFX, but has a high increase at 100 SFX. This pattern is not followed by the growth rate as it increases at 10 SFX and only decreases minimally at 100 SFX.

The final strain 24 has the highest *sul1* copies at a concentration of 10 SFX where it experiences the lowest μ . Strain 24 has the highest growth rate at 100 SFX, although the number of *sul1* copies is smaller by 100 SFX than by 0 SFX.

The following chapter will go further in depth on the observations made by interpreting and analyzing the results.

(a) OD of strain 1 at measured time intervals

(b) OD of strain 2 at measured time intervals

(c) OD of strain 3 at measured time intervals

(d) OD of strain 17 at measured time intervals

(e) OD of strain 21 at measured time intervals

(f) OD of strain 22 at measured time intervals

(g) OD of strain 23 at measured time intervals

(h) OD of strain 24 at measured time intervals

Figure 3.2: OD of all samples at different SFX concentrations from T_0 - T_5

Chapter 4

Discussion

4.1 Interpretation of observations

Sulfamethoxazole antibiotic mode of action relies on competition mechanisms. Thus, possessing a higher number of plasmids encoding for a gene enabling bacteria to survive would be hypothetically beneficial. An increased number of copies would result in a higher expression of the gene and thus, lead to improved resistance against antibiotics. As shown in Figure 3.1 and Table 3.1 there was a general increase of *sul1* copies/ml of broth as the concentration of SFX increased. This observation suggests that with an increase of selective pressure, the number of plasmid copies containing the *sul1* gene increased, supporting the hypothesis.

The observed differences in *sul1* between strains under increased antibiotic selection pressure may result from presence of other resistance mechanisms (e.g. resistance genes). Even though PCR results turned out negative for strains 1-3, qPCR shows that *sul1* was still present, although in smaller numbers. This could be the reason PCR did not detect a strong enough signal for the presence of *sul1*. However, even for strains 1-3 an increase in copies of *sul1* is observable, suggesting that they may also rely on a small number of *sul1* to survive at higher SFX concentrations, even if in total fewer are present compared to the other strains. However, when looking at the results from the second run of qPCR (Tab. D.3 and Tab. 3.12 there are no *sul1* copies present in strain 1, indicating that, as the strain managed to grow at all AB concentration, other resistant mechanisms are ensuring survival. For strain 17, a strong increase in *sul1* copies/ml was observed, especially for 100 mg/L SFX, which is a selective concentration according to the Clinical & Laboratory Standards Institute (CLSI). This suggests, that the main SFX resistance mechanism for strain 17 is based on the *sul1* gene, which thus would require more copies of the gene to survive an increase of antibiotic concentrations.

The other strains that did not show such a drastic increase (strains 22 & 23) in the number

of copies may have other resistance mechanisms and possibly do not rely solely on *sul1*. These could be other *sul* genes such as *sul2*, *sul3* or even others that have not been discovered yet. This is observable in strains 21 and 22 as they, although containing *sul1* according to PCR, do not have as high a number of copies compared to strains 17,23 and 24. There seems to be no need for the bacteria in these strains to increase replication of *sul1*. However, all strains at 100mg/L SFX should have resistance mechanisms encoded in their genetic material, which allow them to survive at a concentration of 100mg/L SFX, according to the CLSI.

When comparing the different strains statistically, Table 3.2 shows that the strains from G1 behave similarly, regardless of the antibiotic concentration, as there is no significant difference, possibly due to them not owning the *sul1* gene in the plasmids and only in the chromosomal DNA. In Table 3.3 with strains 17, 23 and 24 the only significant difference observable occurs at 100mg/L SFX as this is where selective pressure is the highest and depending on the resistant mechanisms the strains react differently. Although strains 21 and 22 do not appear to behave differently in Figure 1, there is a statistically significant difference at all concentrations besides 1 and 10mg/L SFX (Table 3.4). This may be due to not being under selective pressure at the concentrations 1&10, for these strains, and therefore, there is no need to multiply *sul1* copies. Whereas between 0 and 1mg/L SFX the change in environment can trigger the replication of *sul1* to ensure survival at the presence of antibiotics.

The differences in growth rate among the strains could be due to some bacteria actually benefiting from the presence of AB, by using the antibiotics as an energy source and hence increasing their ability, as well as rate, to grow (Reding-Roman et al., 2017). Strains 1, 2, 3, 23 and 24 have a general higher growth rate with increasing AB concentration. This could indicate that these bacteria colonies have adapted well enough to not only be AR, but to also profit from the presence of AB. In general the amount of *sul1* copies present do not seem to influence the growth rate of the strains greatly. However, some strains show a lower growth rate when a higher number of *sul1* copies is present, but one can not say for sure whether this is based on the presence of *sul1*, or if other factors contribute towards the growth rate. There does not seem to be an overall trend visible, indicating that each strain has unique characteristics and attributes contributing to AR and growth rate. Therefore, a general conclusion cannot be drawn from the obtained results which makes searching for a solution against AR an even harder task.

Overall, it can be said that there seems to be a positive correlation between the number of *sul1* copies and the antibiotic concentration which would abide to similar behavior of the *gnrS* genes (Kaplan et al., 2018). The amount of *sul1* genes, however, seems to differ from strain to strain as different types of resistance mechanisms may apply. Based on these results the claim by the World Health Organization is valid, that an increase of AR is a serious health threat (World Health

Organization, 2014), as it shows that all 8 strains managed to grow at 100mg/L SFX and have a form of AR mechanism. Furthermore, this supports the claims of multiple newspaper articles, stating that the need to decrease AB exposure is essential in order to avoid higher development of AR. Studies have shown that countries where there is a lower percentage (5%) of multi-resistant bacteria, such as Norway or Netherlands, prescribe less broad-spectrum antibiotics and rather prescribe antibiotics with specific ranges of effects (Nowotny, 2018). Sulfamethoxazole in combination with trimethoprim is on the World Health Organization's List of Essential Medicines and therefore, a broad-spectrum antibiotic as well as a generic medication (World Health Organization, 2015). It would be wise to reduce the amount of SFX and other antibiotics prescribed by doctors, to avoid further development of multi-resistant bacteria. This is also one of the points the Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development stated in a report in the year 2018 (OECD, 2018) combined with the need of campaigns to raise awareness in order to counter the threat of AR.

4.2 Methodological issues

In order to improve the results and ensure clearer results different limitations have been observed and should be recognized.

4.2.1 Sensitivity of PCR and qPCR

A limitation one can acknowledge is the sensitivity of PCR compared to qPCR. PCR only states whether *sul1* is present or not, but it does not state how much of it is present in each sample. Quantitative PCR (qPCR), on the other hand, detects and states the amount of *sul1* present therefore, enabling quantification of copies. It has a higher accuracy as its theoretical limit of detection is 10 copies/ μL in a DNA extract, meaning that at least 10 copies of *sul1* must be present in order for the machine to distinguish it with a blank value sample. The applied assay had a limit of quantification of around 30 copies/ μL , which is the limit at which the difference between two values can be discerned. The uncertainty of qPCR is difficult to determine, as multiple factors influence the accuracy of the results. This is an issue scientists still struggle with to be able to compare results (Griffiths, Burke, & Emslie, 2011). The qPCR machine detected *sul1* presence Table 3.1 in strains 1-3, after plasmid extraction, which PCR did not. However, this could be due to the gene being present in the chromosome, not in the plasmid, as the plasmid extraction did not extract purely plasmids, as discussed in the next section.

4.2.2 Plasmid extraction

Quantitative PCR detected and quantified *16S rRNA*, which is encoded on the chromosomal bacterial DNA and is applied as a common bacterial marker gene (Anda et al., 2015) (for results refer to the appendix D Table D.1). The limit of detection for *16S rRNA* is 64 copies/ μL and limit of quantification is 200 copies/ μL for qPCR, which is much higher than for *sul1*. The presence of *16S rRNA* indicates that plasmid extraction also resulted in the extraction of chromosomal DNA. However, the values for all strains are very similar indicating that the extraction was stable and the error of the extraction is negligible. Thus, the results of Table 3.1 are not biased by the difference of efficiency of the plasmid extractions and constitute comparable values. In a repetition of the experiment, using a different plasmid extraction kit might result in a cleaner, more accurate extraction and therefore, more precise results.

4.2.3 Number of samples

An additional factor worth considering is the amount of samples checked with qPCR. Only 2 samples per strain (Table D.2) for all concentrations were used and hence a proper analysis of statistical variance is not possible. However, as there is only a limited amount of samples that can be used per qPCR run, which takes over 1h, the total process would take have taken much longer. This was not possible, due to only a limited amount of days being provided in the lab and the qPCR machine not being available at all times. During a repetition of the experiment more samples should be tested to be able to calculate statistical variance and give further insight on patterns and behavior of specific strains.

4.3 Future work

An aspect to consider for future work is investigating other resistant mechanisms allowing *E.coli* to grow at different concentrations of SFX. *FolP* genes present in *E.coli* have shown to also cause sulfonamide resistance (Vedantam & Nichols, 1998). Therefore, it would be of interest to compare the similarity and differences of *sul1* and *folP* genes and whether they occur together and allow survival of bacteria at elevated antibiotic concentrations.

Additionally, it would be of interest to see whether these results hold true for all bacteria or, if it is a unique trait of *E.coli*.

Appendix A

Glossary

16S rRNA	Ribosomal RNA encoded on the DNA of bacteria
AB	Antibiotic
AR	Antibiotic resistance
ARB	Antibiotic resistant bacteria
ARG	Antibiotic resistance gene
CCA	Chromogenic coliform agar
CLSI	Clinical and Laboratory Standard Institute
E.coli	Escherichia coli
folP	Gene causing resistance against sulfonamides
LB	Luria-Bertani, broth for growing bacteria
MM	Master mix, solution serving as basis for PCR
PCR	Polymerase chain reaction
qnrS	Gene causing resistance against quinolone
qPCR	Quantitative polymerase chain reaction
SFX	Sulfamethoxazole
sul1	Gene causing resistance against SFX
WWTP	Waste water treatment plant

Appendix B

Experiment protocol

1. *E. coli* bacteria are isolated from secondary effluent processed in the lab by plating wastewater on Chromogenic Coliform Agar (CCA) supplied with four different concentrations of SFX (0, 1, 10 & 100 mg/L). These concentrations are chosen according to Clinical and Laboratory Standard Institute guidelines (CLSI)(CLSI,2011) to ensure a curve covering the whole range of AB selection pressure. The procedure is as follows.
2. Prepare a broth by adding 250 ml of distilled water to 7.36 g of CCA
3. Heat the broth 30 min till it boils, stir and let it cool down to 60°C
4. Prepare 5 plates for each SFX concentration
5. Prepare a stock concentration of 0.5 g/L of SFX
6. Prepare the different concentrations of SFX for the growth medium and distribute 10ml of ready medium per plate for each concentration of:
 - (a) 0 mg/L of SFX take 50 ml of pure CCA broth,
 - (b) 1 mg/L of SFX take 100 μ L of SFX and add 49.9 ml of CCA,
 - (c) 10 mg/L of SFX take 1 ml of SFX and add 49 ml of CCA,
 - (d) 100 mg/L of SFX take 10 ml of SFX and add 40 ml of CCA,
7. Let the medium cool down until it turns solid.
8. Prepare filtration system and membrane filters, 1 for each plate, to filter the effluent.
9. Dilute the effluent to ensure a reasonable concentration of bacteria, where single colonies can later be picked from.

- (a) Dilution of 10^{-1} : 38 ml saline and 2 ml effluent
 - (b) Dilution of 10^0 : 1 ml of saline and 1 ml of effluent
 - (c) Dilution of 10^1 : 10 ml of effluent
10. For the 0 mg/L and 1 mg/L SFX, 2 plates of dilution 10^{-1} and 1 plate of dilution 10^0 are prepared. Membranes each are plated after filtration. For 10 mg/L and 100 mg/L SFX, 2 plates of dilution 10^0 and 1 plate of dilution 10^{-1} are prepared and membranes placed on the medium after every filtration.
 11. Incubate the plates at 37°C for 24 hours to ensure optimal conditions for *E.coli* to grow.
 12. Prepare a MasterMix (MM) for 30 samples for PCR to check for *sul1* gene:
577.5 μL of H_2O , 75 μL of buffer with MgCl_2 , 15 μL of dNTPs, 37.5 μL of F-primer, 37.5 μL of R-primer and 7.5 μL of TAQ (KAPA Biosystems).
 13. Prepare 24 tubes to pick 6 colonies of *E.coli* per antibiotic (AB) concentration from plates (keep remaining plates for future use), add 25 μL of the MM to each PCR tube and transfer biomass from chosen colonies into tubes with MM.
 14. Run PCR to check for *sul1* gene according to protocol under the conditions specified in Table B.1
 15. Prepare a 2% gel for electrophoresis by adding 1 g of agarose to 50 ml of TAE-buffer.
 16. Fill up the Electrophoresis tank with TAE-buffer and prepare the DNA Loading Dye (1 kb DNA ladder, Invitrogen).
 17. Mix 5 μL of each sample with 1-2 μL of dye and insert in the wells.
 18. Add the Marker for DNA Ladder in the middle of each row as a control group.
 19. Run electrophoresis for 45 min, 60 V, and check for *sul1* gene with an ultraviolet transilluminator.
 20. Pick the same colonies as in step 13 from their plates and put each in 3 ml Luria-Bertani (LB) broth supplied with the same antibiotic concentration as used for isolation of particular strain (0, 1, 10, 100 mg/L SFX)
 21. Incubate samples at 37°C over night.
 22. Pipette 500 μL of each sample with 500 μL of 50% glycerol resulting in 25% glycerol into sealable tubes and store at -20°C .

23. Prepare 250 ml of LB agar and use the 0.5 g/L of SFX stock to get the AB concentrations needed according to the strains tested positively for the *sul1* gene: for 0 mg/L SFX 50 ml of LB, for 1 mg/L SFX 100 μ L of SFX and 49.9 ml of LB, for 10 mg/L SFX 1ml of SFX and 49 ml of LB and for 100 mg/L SFX 10ml SFX and 40 ml of LB.
24. Take the frozen glycerol strains from step 22 and plate them on plates with their according antibiotic medium. Incubate 24h at 37°C.
25. Prepare 200 ml of LB broth and for each strain with *sul1* gene, prepare a falcon tube filled with 10 ml of LB.
26. Spike each tube with the assigned strain of bacteria till it reaches an OD (optical density) of 1. This is done to ensure an equal number of bacterial cells in each sample. (Table 2)
27. Arrange 32 tubes with 8 tubes for each AB concentration (0,1,10,100mg/L SFX) with
 - 0 mg/L SFX are filled with 2.7 ml of LB
 - 1 mg/L SFX are filled with 2.694 ml of LB and 6 μ L of SFX stock
 - 10 mg/L SFX are filled with 2.640 ml of LB and 60 μ L of SFX
 - 100 mg/L SFX are filled with 2.100 ml of LB and 600 μ L of SFX
28. Add 300 μ L of each strain into broth with each SFX concentration (3 control strains and 5 tested strains introduced into 4 tubes with broth and 0, 1, 10 or 100 mg/L SFX)
29. Use E.Z.N.A.® Plasmid DNA Mini Kit I from Omega Bio-Tek for plasmid extraction. Changes in instructions were taken: step 4: a 2-minute incubation; step 9: optional repetition was done for higher purity; between steps 11 & 12: sample tubes are left open to dry for 2 minutes to remove excess ethanol which inhibits qPCR; step 12: 100 μ L Elution Buffer is used
30. Run qPCR with samples. The copy numbers of *sul1* gene are quantified by TaqMan assays, designed and optimized by Ingenetix GmbH (Vienna, Austria) in a Roche Light-Cycler 480 (Roche Applied Science, Germany) in a 10 μ L reaction mixture, containing 1 x LightCycler® 480 Probes Master (Roche, Germany), 1 x TaqMan assay and 2 μ L of a sample. Reactions are run according to the protocol in Table B.2. All samples and standards are assayed in triplicates. Standard curves are prepared for each run by 10-fold dilution of a standard, ranging from 10^7 copies to 10^1 copies.

Table B.1: Protocol for PCR

Step	Nr. of Cycles	Temperature [°C]	Time [sec]
Pre-denaturation	1	95	120
Denaturation	30	95	15
Annealing	30	62	30
Elongation	30	72	45
Final Elongation	1	72	120

Table B.2: Protocol for Quantitative PCR

Step	Nr. of Cycles	Temperature [°C]	Time [sec]
Pre-denaturation	1	95	600
Amplification	45	95	10
		60	30
		72	10
Cooling	1	40	10

Appendix C

Materials used in the experiment

- Bio effluent from Frauenkirchen wastewater treatment plant (WWTP)
- Sulfamethoxazole (SFX)
- Filtration system
- Membrane Filters
- Cell Culture Tubes
- Microcentrifuge Tubes
- INTEGRA Pipetboy with 10 and 20ml pipettes
- Eppendorf® Research® plus pipettes (0.1 – 2.5µL, 2 – 20µL, 10 – 100µL, 100 – 1000µL) and according tips
- Microbiological Incubator
- Hybridization Oven
- Vortex Mixer
- Centrifuge 1-15k
- Electronic scale
- Chromogenic coliform agar (ISO) from VWR BDH Prolabo® Chemicals
- LB Broth from SIGMA® Life Science
- Sodium chloride from SIGMA-ALDRICH®

- peqGOLD Universal Agarose from peqlab
- TAE buffer (50 × pH 8.3 tris-acetate EDTA buffer) from Merck
- LB Broth with agar (Lennox) (LBA) from SIGMA® Life Science
- Equipment and Uncertainty:
 - 0.1 – 2.5µL pipette ± 0.01µL
 - 2 – 20µL pipette ± 0.1µL
 - 10 – 100µL ± 1µL
 - Scale ± 0.001g
 - 10 and 20ml pipette ± 0.1ml

Appendix D

Results from qPCR

Figure D.2 shows the *sul1* signals from qPCR of the samples once the crossing point (Ct) is reached. The higher the Ct value, the less of *sul1* is present. The Ct being the threshold when the fluorescent from amplification exceeds the background fluorescence. At the Ct, the corresponding value (Table 3.1) is then used for calculations. Figure D.1, taken from the qPCR protocol, indicates that there was no contamination in the samples, meaning there is no bias in the results.

Figure D.4 shows the expression of *16S rRNA* present in the tested samples of Figure D.2, indicating that the samples have chromosomal DNA as well, and are not solely composed of plasmids (Table D.1). The negative control Figure D.3 shows that contamination of the sample took place however, as 16S rRNA was not part of the analysis and only posed as a reference to check how accurate the extraction was.

Table D.2 present raw as well as processed data from qPCR that are used for Figure 3.1. It shows the strains, which antibiotic concentration they were exposed to, the number of copies in each well and the number of copies per μL of DNA extract, which are obtained by dividing the number of copies per well by 2, as this was the amount of μL used as a sample. It also shows the quantity of copies per 100 μL of DNA extract, obtained by multiplying the result by 100, as this the amount of Elution Buffer used during plasmid extraction, and it also shows the quantity of copies per ml which, obtained by dividing the number of copies in 100 μL by 2, as, once again, this is the volume used for a sample. Then the results of the 2 samples per strain are used to calculate the average. Then the Log of the resulting numbers is taken and these results are the ones used for the Figure 3.1.

Inc	Pos	Name	Type	CP	Concentration	Standard	Status
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	A1	Sample 1	Negative Control				
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	A2	Sample 2	Negative Control				

Figure D.1: Negative controls for *sul1* with CP being the crossing point

Figure D.2: Report of qPCR showing *sul1* signals

Inc	Pos	Name	Type	CP	Concentration	Standard	Status
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	A1	Sample 1	Negative Control				
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	A2	Sample 2	Negative Control	40.00	4.04E1		>

Figure D.3: Negative controls for *16S rRNA*

Table D.1: Number of 16S copies per strain at different concentrations of SFX

Strain	0 SFX	1 SFX	10 SFX	100 SFX
1	8.50	8.36	8.56	8.65
2	8.50	8.42	8.38	8.43
3	8.70	8.64	8.60	8.70
17	8.18	7.99	8.02	8.65
21	7.97	7.85	8.25	8.51
22	8.47	7.91	8.09	8.74
23	8.41	8.22	8.31	8.62
24	8.10	7.84	7.94	8.74

Figure D.4: Report of qPCR showing 16s signals

Table D.2: Raw and processed data from qPCR

Strain	SFX conc.	Copies / μ L well	Copies / DNA extract $\pm 1\mu$ L	Copies / 100 μ L $\pm 1\mu$ L	Copies / ml ± 0.1 ml	Avg. copies/ml ± 0.1 ml
1	0	9.43E01	4.72E01	4.72E03	2.36E03	2.31E03
1	0	9.03E01	4.52E01	4.52E03	2.26E03	2.31E03
2	0	5.41E02	2.71E02	2.71E04	1.35E04	1.32E04
2	0	5.14E02	2.57E02	2.57E04	1.29E04	1.32E04
3	0	2.89E02	1.45E02	1.45E04	7.23E03	7.03E03
3	0	2.73E02	1.37E02	1.37E04	6.83E03	7.03E03
17	0	1.50E07	7.50E06	7.43E08	3.75E08	3.71E08
17	0	1.47E07	7.35E08	7.43E08	3.68E08	3.71E08
21	0	1.20E07	6.00E08	5.90E08	3.00E08	2.95E08
21	0	1.16E07	5.80E08	5.90E08	2.90E08	2.95E08
22	0	8.80E05	4.40E07	4.56E07	2.20E07	2.28E07
22	0	9.44E05	4.72E07	4.56E07	2.36E07	2.28E07
23	0	1.00E06	5.00E07	5.00E07	2.50E07	2.50E07
23	0	1.00E06	5.00E07	5.00E07	2.50E07	2.50E07
24	0	7.38E06	3.69E08	3.69E08	1.85E08	1.84E08
24	0	7.37E06	3.69E08	3.69E08	1.84E08	1.84E08
1	1	6.91E02	3.46E02	3.46E04	1.73E04	1.67E04
1	1	6.45E02	3.23E02	3.23E04	1.61E04	1.67E04
2	1	1.31E02	6.55E01	6.55E03	3.28E03	3.40E03
2	1	1.41E02	7.05E01	7.05E03	3.53E03	3.40E03
3	1	9.08E01	4.54E01	4.54E03	2.27E03	2.46E03
3	1	1.06E02	5.30E01	5.30E03	2.65E03	2.46E03
17	1	1.00E07	5.00E06	5.00E08	2.50E08	2.51E08
17	1	1.01E07	5.05E06	5.05E08	2.53E08	2.51E08
21	1	1.18E07	5.90E06	5.90E08	2.95E08	2.89E08
21	1	1.13E07	5.65E06	5.65E08	2.83E08	2.89E08
22	1	4.25E05	2.13E05	2.13E07	1.06E07	1.07E07
22	1	4.34E05	2.17E05	2.17E07	1.09E07	1.07E07
23	1	7.14E05	3.57E05	3.57E07	1.79E07	1.76E07
23	1	6.91E05	3.46E05	3.46E07	1.73E07	1.76E07
24	1	8.29E06	4.15E06	4.15E08	2.07E08	2.03E08
24	1	7.98E06	3.99E06	3.99E08	2.00E08	2.03E08
1	10	4.68E02	2.34E02	2.34E04	1.17E04	1.17E04
2	10	5.29E02	2.65E02	2.65E04	1.32E04	1.16E04
2	10	4.00E02	2.00E02	2.00E04	1.00E04	1.16E04
3	10	2.78E02	1.39E02	1.39E04	6.95E03	6.25E03
3	10	2.22E02	1.11E02	1.11E04	5.55E03	6.25E03
17	10	1.22E07	6.10E06	6.10E08	3.05E08	2.96E08
17	10	1.15E07	5.75E06	5.75E08	2.88E08	2.96E08
21	10	2.35E07	1.18E07	1.18E09	5.88E08	5.85E08
21	10	2.33E07	1.17E07	1.17E09	5.83E08	5.85E08
22	10	4.92E05	2.46E05	2.46E07	1.23E07	1.27E07
22	10	5.26E05	2.63E05	2.63E07	1.32E07	1.27E07
23	10	8.49E05	4.25E05	4.25E07	2.12E07	2.10E07
23	10	8.30E05	4.15E05	4.15E07	2.08E07	2.10E07
24	10	8.01E06	4.01E06	4.01E08	2.00E08	2.03E08
24	10	8.25E06	4.13E06	4.13E08	2.06E08	2.03E08
1	100	3.16E03	1.58E03	1.58E05	7.90E04	7.44E04
1	100	2.79E03	1.40E03	1.40E05	6.98E04	7.44E04
2	100	3.12E03	1.56E03	1.56E05	7.80E04	7.35E04
2	100	2.76E03	1.38E03	1.38E05	6.90E04	7.35E04
3	100	1.88E03	9.40E02	9.40E04	4.70E04	4.46E04
3	100	1.69E03	8.45E02	8.45E04	4.23E04	4.46E04
17	100	6.07E07	3.04E07	3.04E09	1.52E09	1.64E09
17	100	7.02E07	3.51E07	3.51E09	1.76E09	1.64E09
21	100	3.69E07	1.85E07	1.85E09	9.23E08	9.29E08
21	100	3.74E07	1.87E07	1.87E09	9.35E08	9.29E08
22	100	1.22E06	6.10E05	6.10E07	3.05E07	3.04E07
22	100	1.21E06	6.05E05	6.05E07	3.03E07	3.04E07
23	100	1.53E06	7.65E05	7.65E07	3.83E07	3.79E07
23	100	1.50E06	7.50E05	7.50E07	3.75E07	3.79E07
24	100	2.07E07	1.04E07	1.04E09	5.18E08	5.09E08
24	100	2.00E07	1.00E07	1.00E09	5.00E08	5.09E08

Table D.3: Raw and processed data from second run of qPCR

Strain	SFX	Abs. quant. <i>sul1</i> copies/ml	average quant. <i>sul1</i> copies/ml	Nr. of cells at T_4 /ml
1	0	5.02E03	5.96E03	6.48E08
1	0	6.91E03	5.96E03	6.48E08
17	0	4.14E08	4.10E08	6.63E08
17	0	4.06E08	4.10E08	6.63E08
21	0	3.27E08	3.24E08	2.23E08
21	0	3.22E08	3.24E08	2.23E08
22	0	1.08E07	1.06E07	3.71E08
22	0	1.04E07	1.06E07	3.71E08
23	0	1.58E07	1.57E07	5.55E08
23	0	1.56E07	1.57E07	5.55E08
24	0	2.09E08	2.08E08	3.12E08
24	0	2.06E08	2.08E08	3.12E08
1	10	8.41E03	6.90E03	5.05E08
1	10	5.39E03	6.90E03	5.05E08
17	10	2.45E08	2.63E08	5.07E08
17	10	2.80E08	2.63E08	5.07E08
21	10	2.05E08	2.06E08	2.10E08
21	10	2.08E08	2.06E08	2.10E08
22	10	2.03E07	2.06E07	2.76E08
22	10	2.09E07	2.06E07	2.76E08
23	10	9.03E06	8.90E06	4.31E08
23	10	8.77E06	8.90E06	4.31E08
24	10	2.13E08	2.18E08	2.70E08
24	10	2.23E08	2.18E08	2.70E08
1	100	2.11E04	1.94E04	5.47E08
1	100	1.77E04	1.94E04	5.47E08
17	100	3.28E08	3.30E08	4.33E08
17	100	3.31E08	3.30E08	4.33E08
21	100	1.69E08	1.70E08	2.06E08
21	100	1.72E08	1.70E08	2.06E08
22	100	2.00E07	2.02E07	2.74E08
22	100	2.03E07	2.02E07	2.74E08
23	100	3.25E07	3.19E07	4.81E08
23	100	3.13E07	3.19E07	4.81E08
24	100	1.53E08	1.53E08	2.40E08
24	100	1.52E08	1.53E08	2.40E08

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